

PROPERTIES OF IRRESOLUTE – BITOPOLOGICAL GROUPS

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Abstract:

In this paper, we introduce and study a class of bitopologized groups called (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological groups.

1. Introduction:

If $(G, *)$ is a group, τ_1 and τ_2 are topologies on G , then we say that $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is a bitopologized group. Given a bitopologized group G , a question arises about interactions and relations between algebraic and bitopological structures: which topological properties are satisfied by the multiplication mapping $m : G \times G \rightarrow G, (x, y) \rightarrow x * y$, and the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G, x \rightarrow x^{-1}$. In this paper, we introduce and study a class of bitopologized groups called (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological groups.

2. Preliminaries:

Throughout this paper $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, or simply G , will denote a group $(G, *)$ endowed with the topologies τ_1 and τ_2 on G . The identity element of G is denoted by e , or e_G when it is necessary, the operation $*$: $G \times G \rightarrow G, (x, y) \rightarrow x * y$, is called the multiplication mapping and sometimes denoted by m , and the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G, x \rightarrow x^{-1}$ is denoted by i . For a subset A of a topological space (X, τ_i) , $iCl(A)$ and $iInt(A)$ denote the closure of A and interior of A in (X, τ_i) , respectively.

Definition 2.1: [2] A subset S of a bitopological space (X, τ_1, τ_2) , is said to be (i, j) -semiopen if $S \subset jCl(iInt(S))$. The complement of an (i, j) -semiopen set is called an (i, j) -semiclosed set.

Definition 2.2: [2] The intersection of all (i, j) -semiclosed sets containing $S \subset X$ is called the (i, j) -semiclosure of S and is denoted by $(i, j)-sCl(S)$. The family of all (i, j) -semiopen (resp. (i, j) -semiclosed) sets of (X, τ_1, τ_2) , is denoted by $(i, j)-SO(X)$ (resp. $(i, j)-SC(X)$). The family of all (i, j) -semiopen (resp. (i, j) -semiclosed) sets of (X, τ_1, τ_2) , containing a point $x \in X$ is denoted by $(i, j)-SO(X, x)$ (resp. $(i, j)-SC(X, x)$).

Definition 2.3: A function $f : (X, \tau_1, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ is said to be :

1. (i, j) -semicontinuous [2] if $f^{-1}(V) \in (i, j)-SO(X)$ for every $V \in \sigma_i$.
2. (i, j) -irresolute [1] if $f^{-1}(V) \in (i, j)-SO(X)$ for every $V \in (i, j)-SO(Y)$.
3. pre- (i, j) -semiopen if $f(V) \in (i, j)-SO(Y)$ for every $V \in (i, j)-SO(X)$.
4. (i, j) -semihomomorphism if f is bijective, (i, j) -irresolute and pre- (i, j) -semiopen.

Lemma 2.4:

If $f : (X, \tau_1, \tau_2) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma_1, \sigma_2)$ is an (i, j) -semihomomorphism, then,

1. $(i, j)-sCl(f(A)) = f((i, j)-sCl(A))$ for all $A \subset X$.
2. $(i, j)-sInt(f(A)) = f((i, j)-sInt(A))$ for all $A \subset X$.

3. Irresolute - Bitopological Groups:

Definition 3.1: A bitopologized group $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, is called an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group if for each $x, y \in G$ and each (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood W of $x * y$

y^{-1} in G there exists (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods U of x and V of y such that $U * V^{-1} \subset W$.

Lemma 3.2:

If $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group then we have the following

1. $A \in (i, j)$ -SO (G) if, and only if $A^{-1} \in (i, j)$ -SO (G) .
2. If $A \in (i, j)$ -SO (G) and $B \subset G$, then $A * B, B * A \in (i, j)$ -SO (G) .

Proof:

The proof is clear.

Theorem 3.3:

If $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group, then the multiplication mapping $m : G \times G \rightarrow G$ and the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G$ are (i, j) -irresolute.

Proof:

Let $(x, y) \in G \times G$ and let $W \subset G$ be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $m(x, y) = x * y$. Since G is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group, and W is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $x * (y^{-1})^{-1}$, there exist (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods U of x and V of y^{-1} such that $U * V^{-1} \subset W$. From Lemma 3.2, V^{-1} is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of y , and $U * V^{-1}$ is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $(x, y) \in G \times G$. Then $m(U * V^{-1}) \subset W$ just means that m is irresolute at (x, y) , and, as (x, y) was an arbitrary point in $G \times G$, that m is (i, j) -irresolute on $G \times G$. For i is (i, j) -irresolute, let $x \in G$ be a point and let W be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $i(x) = x^{-1}$, Then by Lemma 3.2, W^{-1} is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of x satisfying $i(W^{-1}) = W$, which means that i is (i, j) -irresolute at x , hence on G .

Remark 3.4: If $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$, is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group such that the family (i, j) -SO (G) is a topology on G with (i, j) -SO $(G) \neq \tau_i$ then $(G, *, (i, j)$ -SO $(G))$ is a topological group.

Theorem 3.5:

Let $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ be an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group and $(H, o, \tau_1|H, \tau_2|H)$ a bitopological group. If $f : G \rightarrow H$ is a pairwise homeomorphism and (i, j) -semihomomorphism, then H is also an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group.

Proof:

Let x and y any two points in H and let $W \subset H$ be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $x o y^{-1}$, Let $a = f^{-1}(x)$, $b = f^{-1}(y)$. Since f is an (i, j) -irresolute mapping, the set $f^{-1}(W)$ is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $a * b^{-1}$ and G is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group there are (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods A and B of a and b , respectively with $A * B^{-1} \subset f^{-1}(W)$. Pre- (i, j) -semiopenness of f implies that the sets $U = f(A)$ and $V = f(B)$ are (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods of x and y that satisfy $U o V^{-1} = f(A) o f(B)^{-1} = f(A * B^{-1}) \subset W$. This means that $(H, o, \tau_1|H, \tau_2|H)$ is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological groups.

Theorem 3.6:

Let $f : G \rightarrow H$ be a pairwise homeomorphism, where $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ and $(H, o, \tau_1|H, \tau_2|H)$ be (i, j) -irresolute bitopological groups. If f is (i, j) -irresolute at the neutral element e_G of G then f is (i, j) -irresolute on G .

Proof:

Let $x \in G$ be an arbitrary element, and let W be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $y = f(x)$ in H . Since the left translations in H are (i, j) -semihomomorphisms, there is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood V of the neutral element e_H of H such that $l_y(V) = y o V \subset W$. From (i, j) -irresoluteness of f at e_G it follows the existence of an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood U of e_G such that $f(U) \subset V$. But $l_x : G \rightarrow G$ is a pre- (i, j) -semiopen mapping, so that the set $x * U$ is an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of x , for which we

have $f(x * U) = f(x) \circ f(U) = y \circ f(U) \subset y \circ V \subset W$: Hence f is (i, j) -irresoltr at the point x of G , and since x was an arbitrary element in G , f is (i, j) -irresolute on G .

Theorem 3.7:

*Every biopen subgroup H of an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ is also an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group.*

Proof:

We prove that for each $x, y \in H$ and each (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood $W \subset H$ of $x * y^{-1}$ there exist (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods $U \subset H$ of x and $V \subset H$ of y such that $U * V^{-1} \subset W$. Since H is biopen, and W is (i, j) -semiopen in G , the set $W \cap H = W$ is an (i, j) -semiopen in G and contains $x * y^{-1}$. Apply now the fact that G is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group to find (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood A of x and B of y such that $A * B^{-1} \subset W$. The sets $U = A \cap H$ and $V = B \cap H$ are (i, j) -semiopen subsets of H which contain x and y satisfy $U * V^{-1} \subset A * B^{-1} \subset W$, which means that H is an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group.

Theorem 3.8:

A nonempty subgroup H of an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group G is (i, j) -semiopen if, and only if its (i, j) -semiinterior is nonempty.

Proof:

Assume $x \in (i, j)$ -s $Int(H)$. There is an (i, j) -semiopen set V such that $x \in V \subset H$. This implies $x * V \subset H$. For every $y \in H$ we have $y * V = y * x^{-1} * x * V \subset y * x^{-1} * H = H$. Since $y * V$ is (i, j) -semiopen we conclude that $H = \cup \{y * V : y \in H\}$ is (i, j) -semiopen as the union of (i, j) -semiopen sets. The converse is trivial.

Theorem 3.9:

*Let $(G, *, \tau_1, \tau_2)$ be an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group. Then every biopen subgroup of G is (i, j) -semiclosed in G .*

Proof:

Let H be a biopen subgroup of G . Then every left coset $x * H$ of H is (i, j) -semiopen because l_x is a pre- (i, j) -semiopen mapping. Thus, $Y = \cup_{x \in G \setminus H} x * H$ is also (i, j) -semiopen as a union of (i, j) -semiopen sets. Then $H = G \setminus Y$ is (i, j) -semiclosed.

Theorem 3.10:

Let U be a symmetric (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of the identity e in an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group G . Then the set $L = \cup_{n=1}^{\infty} U^n$ is an (i, j) -semiopen and (i, j) -semiclosed subgroup of G .

Proof:

It is easy to see that L is a subgroup of G : if $x \in U^p, y \in U^q$ are element from L , then $x * y \in U^{p+q} \subset L$; if $x \in L$; say $x \in U^k$, then $x^{-1} \in (U^{-1})^k = U^k \subset L$. Because all translations in G are pre- (i, j) -semiopen mappings, U^n is (i, j) -semiopen for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and thus also L is (i, j) -semiopen in G . By Theorem 3.9, L is (i, j) -semiclosed.

Corollary 3.11:

Let G be an (i, j) -irresolute bitopological group, and μ_e the collection of all (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods of e . Then

- 1) *for every $U \in \mu_e$, there is a $V \in \mu_e$ such that $V^{-1} \subset U$;*
- 2) *for every $U \in \mu_e$ and every $x \in U$, there is $V \in \mu_e$ such that $x * V \subset U$.*

Proof:

(1). It follows from the fact that the inverse mapping i is (i, j) -irresolute and $i(e) = e$.

(2). This is follows from : ' x is an (i, j) -semihomomorphism, and $l_x(e) = x$, so that there is a neighbourhood V of e such that $l_x(V) \subset U$, that is, $x * V \subset U$.

Theorem 3.12:

Let G be an (i, j) -irresolute bitopological group, $A \subset G$ and μ_e the system of all (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of e . Then (i, j) -s $Cl(A) = \cap \{A * U : U \in \mu_e\}$.

Proof:

Let $x \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)$ and let U be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of e . The inverse mapping i is (i, j) -irresolute, so that $i(e) = e$ implies the existence of an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood V of e such that $i(V) = V^{-1} \subset U$. From $x * V \cap A \neq \emptyset$, it follows that for some $v \in V$ and some $a \in A$ it holds $a = x * v$, that is, $x = a * v^{-1} \in A * V^{-1} \subset A * U$. As U is an arbitrary element from μ_e it follows (i, j) -s $Cl(A) \subset \cap \{A * U : U \in \mu_e\}$. Conversely, let $x \notin (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)$. Then there exists $V \in \mu_e$ such that $x * V \cap A = \emptyset$. Pick an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood U of e such that $U^{-1} \subset V$; the existence of such a set U follows from the (i, j) -irresoluteness of the inverse mapping i at e . Then $(x * U^{-1}) \cap A = \emptyset$, thus $x \notin A * U$. Therefore, $\cap \{A * U : U \in \mu_e\} \subset (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)$, and the theorem is proved.

Theorem 3.13:

Let A and B be subset of an (i, j) -irresolute-bitopological group G . Then we have the following

1. (i, j) -s $Cl(A) * (i, j)$ -s $Cl(B) \subset (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A * B)$;
2. $((i, j)$ -s $Cl(A))^{-1} = (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A^{-1})$;
3. (i, j) -s $Int(A)^{-1} = (i, j)$ -s $Int(A^{-1})$.

Proof:

(1). Suppose that $x \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)$, $y \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(B)$. Let W be an (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhood of $x * y$. Then there are (i, j) -semiopen neighbourhoods U and V of x and y . Such that $U * V \subset W$. Since $x \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)$, $y \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(B)$, there are $a \in A \cap U$ and $b \in B \cap V$. Then $a * b \in (A * B) \cap (U * V) \subset (A * B) \subset W$. This means $x * y \in (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A * B)$, that is, we have (i, j) -s $Cl(A) * (i, j)$ -s $Cl(B) \subset (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A * B)$.

(2). Since the inverse mapping $i : G \rightarrow G$ is an (i, j) -semihomomorphism, then by Lemma 2.4 we have (i, j) -s $Cl(i(A)) = (i, j)$ -s $Cl(A^{-1}) = i((i, j)$ -s $Cl(A)) = ((i, j)$ -s $Cl(A))^{-1}$.

(3). Since the inverse mapping i is an (i, j) -semihomomorphism, which by Lemma 2.4 gives (i, j) -s $Int(A^{-1}) = (i, j)$ -s $Int(A)^{-1}$.

References:

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